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Synthesis, characterization, molecular modeling and antimicrobial activities of Copper(II) complex of 4-aminoantipyrine

Uche G. Nwokeke¹ and Godspower O. Nwanekwu^{2,*}

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

² Inorganic, Coordination, Molecular Modeling, Drug Design and Discovery Research Group, Department of Chemistry, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

*E-mail address: nwanekwugodspower818@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A Copper(II) complex of 4-aminoantipyrine (4-AAP) was synthesized in ethanol and characterized using a combination of physicochemical and spectroscopic techniques, including solubility tests, melting point determination, Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, UV-Visible spectroscopy, and molecular modeling studies. The complex was soluble in ethanol, methanol, and DMSO, but insoluble in water. The melting points of the ligand (230 °C) and its complex (340 °C) indicate enhanced thermal stability upon coordination with Cu(II). FT-IR spectral data revealed shifts in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ bands, confirming that the ligand coordinates to the copper center through both the carbonyl oxygen and amine nitrogen atoms, acting as a bidentate donor. Additionally, water was found to participate in coordination, completing the metal's coordination sphere. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were performed at the B3LYP-D3/LACVP** level to optimize the geometry of the complex and evaluate its electronic properties. The theoretical data showed Cu–O and Cu–N bond lengths in the range of 1.84-2.26 Å and 1.89 Å, respectively, consistent with experimental observations. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap (2.78 eV) and global reactivity descriptors indicated good stability and moderate chemical reactivity of the complex, in agreement with literature reports on 4-AAP systems. The in vitro antimicrobial activity of the complex was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using the agar diffusion method. The complex exhibited markedly higher antibacterial activity than the free ligand, suggesting that coordination enhances the bioactivity of 4-AAP.

Keywords: Metal complex, 4-Aminoantipyrine, 4-AAP, Antimicrobial activities, Copper(II) complex, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, antipyrine and its derivatives have received significant attention in the field of chemistry. These compounds have been found to possess a range of biological properties, including analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects, as well as antiviral, antibacterial, and herbicidal activities [1]. Coordination of organic compounds with metal, i.e. chelation causes drastic change in the biological property of the ligand and also the metal moiety. It has been reported that chelation is the cause and cure of many diseases including cancer [2]. Metal ions play a vital role in a wide range of biological processes, thanks to their variable oxidation states and coordination numbers, which allow them to form covalent interactions with biomolecules [3]. In the human body, these ions are essential for maintaining homeostasis and supporting numerous physiological functions.

They often act as cofactors for proteins, helping to stabilize their structures, regulate their activities, and facilitate essential cellular tasks [4, 5]. The body has developed sophisticated mechanisms to manage the distribution and transport of metal ions efficiently [6, 7]. Beyond their regulatory roles, metal ions also contribute to catalytic and structural functions at the molecular level [8, 9]. Recent advances in medicine have highlighted the therapeutic potential of metal ions, either on their own or in coordination with organic ligands as promising agents in the treatment of cancer and various infectious diseases [10, 11]. The growing resistance of microbes to current antibiotics has made the search for new compounds with potential antibacterial and antifungal effects more urgent than ever [12].

Figure 1. Structure of 4-aminoantipyrine.

Some of the biggest breakthroughs in medicinal chemistry have come from the use of heterocyclic compounds, which are known to play a crucial role in regulating various biological activities. Heterocyclic moieties can be found in a large number of compounds which display biological activity. Among them, antipyrine – a nitrogen – containing heterocyclic compound – and its derivatives stand out for their diverse biological activities and wide-ranging

applications [13, 14]. Antipyrine and its derivatives have also been used as additives in hair coloring products and in the spectrophotometric detection of metal ions. They are particularly valuable as potential ligands for constructing polynuclear complexes, which can serve as models for bioinorganic systems and as a starting point for developing new catalyst precursors [15, 16]. In this study, we present the synthesis, characterization, and molecular modeling of Cu(II) complex of 4-aminoantipyrine. This work builds on the ongoing interest in using transition metal complexes to treat human diseases, especially in response to the growing global challenge of multidrug – resistant microorganisms.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification. The determination of the melting point of the complex was performed using the Gallenkamp melting point apparatus at the Department of Chemistry, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria, while solubility was determined in the following solvents: ethanol, methanol, DMSO and distilled water. The infra-red spectroscopy was carried out using KBr pellets within 4,000 – 400 cm^{-1} range spectrophotometers at National Research Institute for Chemical Technology, Zaria, Nigeria. The Ultraviolet – visible spectra of the complex was recorded on a Shimadzu UV/Vis 2401 spectrophotometer within the range of 200 – 800 nm.

2. 1. Synthesis of the complex

The complex was synthesized based on a previously reported method, with slight modifications [17]. 15 mL of an ethanolic solution containing 4-aminoantipyrine (3 mmol) was added slowly, drop by drop, to 25 mL of an aqueous solution of Copper(II) chloride (1 mmol) under constant stirring. The resulting mixture was then refluxed for 4 hours and allowed to cool to room temperature. A yellowish-colored powder gradually formed, which was collected by filtration.

2. 2. Antibacterial Screening

To assess the antimicrobial activity of the synthesized complex, a standard agar diffusion method was used. Seven grams of nutrient agar were measured and dissolved in 250 ml of distilled water inside a conical flask. The flask was then sealed with cotton wool and covered with aluminum foil before being sterilized in an autoclave. Once the agar had solidified in Petri dishes, selected bacterial strains, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, were carefully inoculated onto the surface. Using a sterilized cork borer (about 5 mm in diameter), wells were made in the center of each agar plate. Each well was filled with the test solutions of the synthesized complex at a concentration of 20 ppm. The plates were left undisturbed for 30 minutes to allow the compound to diffuse properly into the agar. After that, they were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Following incubation, the zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters and recorded for analysis [18].

2. 3. Molecular Modeling

Molecular modeling was carried out to better understand the geometric and electronic properties of the ligand and its metal complex. Geometry optimization and electronic structure

calculations were performed using the Jaguar software package (Schrödinger), based on density functional theory (DFT) methods [19]. All computations employed the B3LYP-D3 functional with the LACVP** basis set.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesized complex was obtained in good yields and appeared as a crystalline, coloured, and air-stable material. Its high stability can be attributed to its polydentate nature. The proposed structure of the 4-aminoantipyrine metal (II) complex is shown in **Figure 2**, while the physical properties of the parent ligand and its metal complex are summarized in **Table 1**. The parent ligand, 4-aminoantipyrine, had a melting point of 230-231 °C, whereas the new complex exhibited a higher melting point, indicating enhanced thermal stability compared to the free ligand.

Table 1. Physical properties of the ligand and its metal complex.

Compound	Product yield (%)	Colour	M.P (°C)	Physical Appearance
Ligand (4 – AAP)	-	Yellowish brown	230 – 231	Powdery
Complex [Cu (4 – AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	71	Dark blue	339 – 340	Crystalline

M.P – Melting Point

Table 2. Solubility of the ligand and its metal complex in different solvents.

Compound	Distilled water	Ethanol	Methanol	DMSO
Ligand (4 – AAP)	NS	S	S	S
Complex [Cu (4 – AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	NS	S	S	S

3. 1. Conductance Studies

Conductivity measurements in non-aqueous solutions are widely used in structural studies of metal chelates, provided the complexes are sufficiently soluble. These measurements offer insight into the degree of ionization of a complex in solution. Generally, the greater the number of ions a complex release, the higher its molar conductivity [20]. In contrast, non-ionized or neutral complexes exhibit very low molar conductance values. In this study, the copper complex

showed a molar conductance of $7.35 \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ in a non-aqueous medium, suggesting that it behaves as a non-electrolyte.

Figure 2. Proposed structure of Copper complex of 4-Aminoantipyrine.

3. 2. Infrared absorption spectra

The infrared spectra of the synthesized complex and its ligand are presented in **Figure 3**. **Table 3** shows the selected infrared absorption frequencies of the ligand and the complex. The characteristic functional groups bands of the parent ligand was compared to those of the synthesized complex. On complex formation most of the bands in the IR spectrum of the ligand 4-aminoantipyrine undergo frequency shift and in many cases intensity changes. A medium band approximately at 3408 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ Stretch [21]. This bands shows an upward shift by about (12 cm^{-1}) in the spectrum of the complex, indicating the possibility of 4-aminoantipyrine coordinating through the nitrogen atom of the amine. Absorption assigned for $\nu(\text{N-N})$ was noticed at 1060 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the complex with changes in intensity [22]. While the absorption band caused by $\nu(\text{C=O})$ appeared at 1442.80 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complex shifted to lower frequency by ($8 - 25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which might indicate the coordination of carbonyl group to the center metal ion [23]. Additionally, a band observed near 1600 cm^{-1} corresponds to the H-O-H bending vibration [24], supporting the presence of water within the coordination sphere, contributing to the octahedral geometry

of the complex. The IR spectral study suggests that the 4-aminoantipyrine ligand coordinate with Cu in bidentate fashion with the metal ion surrounded by ligand in octahedral manner.

Table 3. Infrared data (cm^{-1}) of the ligand and its metal complex.

Compound	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{HOH})$
Ligand (4 – AAP)	3408	1450	1050	1600
Complex [Cu (4 – AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3420	1442	1060	1575

Figure 3. FTIR Spectra of the Ligand (a) and its copper complex (b).

3. 3. UV-visible absorption

The Ultraviolet-visible spectra of the ligand and its complex are indicated in **Figure 4.1** and **4.2** respectively. **Figure 4.1** shows the absorption maximum wavelength of

4-aminoantipyrene. The absorption maxima was observed at 345 nm and absorbance at 2.147 which may be attributed to the moderate energy ($\pi - \pi^*$) transitions of the aromatic rings. **Figure 4.2** shows the absorption maximum wavelength of Cu (4-aminoantipyrene) complex. The absorption maxima was observed at 364 nm and absorbance at 2.249.

Figure 4.1. UV-visible spectrum of the ligand.

Figure 4.2. UV-visible spectrum of the synthesized complex.

3. 4. Antimicrobial Activities

The antimicrobial evaluation of the synthesized Cu(II) complex of 4-aminoantipyridine demonstrated a marked improvement in activity compared to the free ligand across all tested bacterial strains. As seen in **Figure 5**, the complex exhibited significantly larger zones of inhibition, indicating enhanced efficacy upon coordination with the metal ion. This increased activity can be attributed to metal coordination. When 4-aminoantipyridine binds with Cu(II), the resulting complex likely becomes more lipophilic, allowing it to more easily pass through the bacterial cell membrane.

Figure 5. Antimicrobial Activity of the Ligand and the Cu (II) Complex.

This improved permeability enhances its ability to disrupt microbial functions more effectively than the ligand alone. Similar observations have been reported in previous studies, where metal complexes of Schiff base ligands showed higher antimicrobial potential due to increased stability and better interaction with biological targets [25], observed that Cu(II) complexes of 4-aminoantipyridine Schiff bases showed superior antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* compared to uncomplexed ligands. In a separate study, Sherif et al (2021) reported comparable trends with 4-aminoantipyridine derivatives: their Cu(II) complexes exhibited larger zones of inhibition against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa* [26].

Among the tested strains, the complex showed the most pronounced activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, with inhibition zones reaching up to 22 mm and 20 mm respectively. This suggests the complex is effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, though with slightly greater sensitivity observed in the Gram-positive strain (*S. aureus*). The lowest activity was recorded against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which is known for its resistance to many antimicrobial agents due to its robust outer membrane and efflux mechanisms.

Overall, the results support the idea that complexation with Cu(II) enhances the antimicrobial efficacy of 4-aminoantipyrine. These observations suggest potential for further development of metal-based drug candidates using 4-aminoantipyrine as a ligand framework.

Table 4. Antimicrobial activities of the ligand and its metal complex.

Compound	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
	Zones of Inhibition (mm)			
Ligand (4 – AAP)	11	12	15	9
Complex [Cu(4-AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	19	20	22	17

3. 5. Molecular Modeling

To gain deeper insight into the structural and electronic properties of the synthesized copper complex, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were carried out. The geometry of both the free ligand and its metal complex was optimized using the B3LYP-D3 functional with the LACVP** basis set, as implemented in the Jaguar program (Schrödinger) [19]. All optimized structures were confirmed to be true minima through vibrational frequency analysis, showing no imaginary frequencies. The calculated total energy, as well as the HOMO and LUMO values obtained after geometry optimization of the ligand and complex structures are presented in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Energy Properties of the Ligand and Synthesized Cu (II) Complex.

Compounds	Total Energy (Kcal/mol)	Electronic Energy (Kcal/mol)	HOMO(eV)	LUMO(eV)
Ligand (4-AAP)	-413036.42	-918508.40	-7.34	-4.59
[Cu(4-AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	-1045230.77	-2990318.41	-6.77	-3.99

Density functional theory (DFT) was used to determine the total electronic energies (E_T) of the optimized structures of the ligand and the copper (II) complex (**Figure 6 and 7**).

Figure 6. Molecular structure of 4-AAP along with the atom numbering scheme.

The fully optimized compound, $[\text{Cu}(\text{4AAP})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, displayed a total energy of -1045230.77 eV, whereas the ligand (4-aminoantipyrine) displayed a total energy of -413036.42 eV. The stability brought about by coordination between the Cu ion and the donor atoms of the ligand and water molecules is reflected in the complex's noticeably higher negative total energy when compared to the free ligand. This stabilization aligns with the development of a coordination complex that is thermodynamically advantageous [27].

Figure 7. Molecular structure of $[\text{Cu}(\text{4-AAP})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ along with the atom numbering scheme.

Table 6. Bond lengths for Cu(II) Complex.

Atoms	Bond lengths (Å)	Atoms	Bond lengths (Å)
C1-C2	1.381629	C19-C20	1.267391
C1-C6	1.497800	C20-C21	1.378454
C1-N7	1.375420	C21-C29	1.443222
C2-C3	1.272862	N22-N23	1.433876
C3-C4	1.322560	N22-C26	1.362321
C4-C51	266037	N23-C24	1.405048
C5-C6	1.381066	N23-C29	1.323147
C6-C14	1.443687	C24-C25	1.564437
N7-N8	1.429092	C24-C28	1.318841
N7-C11	1.367993	C25-C26	1.551972
N8-C9	1.408165	C25-N27	1.227263
N8-C14	1.324502	C26-O30	1.215038
C9-C10	1.517662	N27-Cu31	1.891905
C9-C13	1.325049	Cu31-O32	1.843152
C10-C11	1.534235	Cu31-O35	2.011849
C10-N12	1.251284	O32-H34	0.960521
C11-O15	1.210589	O35-H36	0.959324
N12-H33	1.052249	O35-H37	0.986972
O15-Cu31	2.257543	C16-N22	1.378548
C16-C17	1.386856	C17-C18	1.274819
C16-C21	1.492179	C18-C19	1.323923

3. 6. Bond length and Bond angle

The optimized geometry of the [Cu(4AAP)₂(H₂O)₂] complex, obtained using Density Functional Theory (DFT), provides valuable insight into the coordination environment and molecular structure around the copper(II) center. The calculated bond lengths and bond angles

are consistent with a distorted octahedral geometry, which is typical of Cu(II) complexes due to Jahn–Teller distortion effects [28]. From the DFT data (**Table 6**), the Cu–O and Cu–N bond lengths were found in the range of 1.84-2.26 Å and 1.89 Å, respectively. These values indicate strong coordination between the copper(II) ion and the oxygen atoms of the coordinated water molecules, as well as with the nitrogen atoms of the 4-aminoantipyridine ligands.

The relatively longer Cu–O bond length (2.011-2.257 Å) compared to Cu–N suggests that the nitrogen donors provide slightly stronger bonding interactions, which may arise from their greater ligand field stabilization contribution. This observation agrees with previously reported data for Cu(II)–4AAP and similar N,O-chelating systems, where Cu–N bonds typically fall between 1.85-1.95 Å, and Cu–O bonds are slightly longer due to partial ionic character [29]. The intraligand bond distances within the 4AAP moiety show typical aromatic and C–N bond lengths (1.27-1.43 Å), confirming that coordination does not significantly disrupt the ligand’s aromatic framework.

The observed N–N and C–N bond distances (1.36-1.43 Å) suggest partial delocalization of π -electrons within the pyrazolone ring system, consistent with the conjugated nature of the 4-aminoantipyridine ligand. The stability of these bonds further supports efficient electron donation from the ligand to the metal center through both nitrogen and oxygen atoms.

Table 7. Bond angles for Cu(II) Complex.

Atoms	Angles (°)	Atoms	Angles (°)
C6-C1-C2	123.021077	C20-C19-C18	111.585765
N7-C1-C2	132.730476	C21-C20-C19	128.951928
N7-C1-C6	104.248448	C20-C21-C16	110.249384
C3-C2-C1	110.628883	C29-C21-C16	110.545155
C4-C3-C2	133.997991	C29-C21-C20	139.205461
C5-C4-C3	114.721260	N23-N22-C16	106.725191
C6-C5-C4	126.746327	C26-N22-C16	139.756500
C5-C6-C1	110.884463	C26-N22-N23	113.518309
C14-C6-C1	110.324426	C24-N23-N22	109.267626
C14-C6-C5	138.791112	C29-N23-N22	115.929550
N8-N7-C1	106.823562	C29-N23-C24	134.802823
C11-N7-C1	139.850567	C25-C24-N23	107.138470
C11-N7-N8	113.325871	C28-C24-N23	127.016337
C9-N8-N7	108.429728	C28-C24-C25	125.845193

C14-N8-N7	116.159559	C26-C25-C24	103.202212
C14-N8-C9	135.410713	N27-C25-C24	129.042926
C10-C9-N8	107.542316	N27-C25-C26	127.754863
C13-C9-N8	127.299542	C25-C26-N22	106.873383
C13-C9-C10	125.158143	O30-C26-N22	125.972251
C11-C10-C9	104.753837	O30-C26-C25	127.154366
N12-C10-C9	128.671826	Cu31-N27-C25	148.111042
N12-C10-C11	126.574337	N23-C29-C21	102.555590
C10-C11-N7	105.948249	N27-Cu31-O15	82.359552
O15-C11-N7	125.358392	O32-Cu31-O15	84.992371
O15-C11-C10	128.693360	O32-Cu31-N27	167.351922
H33-N12-C10	112.195796	O35-Cu31-O15	178.606105
N8-C14-C6	102.444006	O35-Cu31-N27	96.246553
Cu31-O15-C11	149.367347	O35-Cu31-O32	96.401525
C21-C16 -C17	123.350801	H34-O32-Cu31	116.775357
N22-C16 -C17	132.404686	H36-O35-Cu31	131.348110
N22-C16-C21	104.244513	H37-O35-Cu31	116.425062
C18-C17-C16	109.156246	H37-O35-H36	112.226827

The calculated bond angles (**Table 7**) further corroborate the distorted octahedral geometry. The O–Cu–O and N–Cu–O angles range between 82° – 96°, while the N–Cu–N and O–Cu–N angles vary between 84° – 148°, showing noticeable deviation from the ideal 90° and 180° values expected for a perfect octahedron. This deviation arises from the asymmetric ligand coordination and the constraints imposed by the bidentate nature of the 4AAP ligands. The observed angular distortions are characteristic of Cu (II) complexes with mixed donor atoms (N and O), where spatial and electronic factors contribute to geometric distortion [30, 31].

3. 7. Molecular Orbitals and Reactivity Descriptors

The molecular orbitals (MOs), including the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of the free ligand and its metal complex, are presented in **Figures 8 and 9**. These frontier orbitals provide valuable insights into the electronic structure and potential reactivity of the molecules [32]. Key global reactivity descriptors such as; chemical potential (μ), chemical hardness (η), and electrophilicity index

(ω), including the energy gap, to understand the reactivity and the stability were calculated using the energies of the HOMO and LUMO and are summarized in **Table 8**. All geometry optimizations and electronic structure calculations were performed using density functional theory (DFT) at the B3LYP-D3/LACVP** level of theory as implemented in the Schrödinger Jaguar suite [19]. The HOMO–LUMO surfaces were visualized to further understand the charge distribution and reactivity patterns within the molecules.

Table 8. Global Reactivity Descriptors.

Compound	Homo (eV)	Lumo (eV)	ΔE (eV)	μ (eV)	H (eV)	Ω (eV)
4-AAP	-7.34	-4.59	2.75	-5.96	1.36	12.94
[Cu(4-AAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	-6.77	-3.99	2.78	-5.38	1.39	10.41

Figure 8. HOMO and LUMO surfaces of the ligand 4-AAP.

Figure 9. HOMO and LUMO surfaces of the Cu(4AAP) Complex.

The HOMO and LUMO energies calculated for the free ligand and its copper(II) complex show only modest changes on coordination, but those small shifts carry chemically meaningful information. Complexation raises both frontier orbitals (HOMO: $-7.34 \rightarrow -6.77 \text{ eV}$; LUMO: $-4.59 \rightarrow -3.99 \text{ eV}$), i.e. both frontier levels become less negative, while the HOMO–LUMO gap remains essentially unchanged ($\Delta E \approx 2.75 \rightarrow 2.78 \text{ eV}$). This pattern is chemically reasonable as coordination of 4-AAP to Cu(II) donates electron density into the metal center and perturbs the ligand π -system, which typically shifts ligand-based orbitals upward in energy [33]. The near-constant gap indicates that the ligand's conjugated framework remains electronically intact after coordination and that the complex preserves a comparable frontier orbital separation to the free ligand.

The computed chemical potential (μ) becomes less negative on complexation ($-5.97 \rightarrow -5.38 \text{ eV}$). A less negative μ reflects a slightly reduced global tendency to attract additional

electron density indicating that the complex is marginally less electron-hungry than the isolated ligand. Chemical hardness (η) increases only slightly ($1.375 \rightarrow 1.39$ eV), indicating a subtle increase in resistance to charge-transfer deformation; that is, the complex is marginally “harder” but changes are very small and within expected computational variability. The electrophilicity index (ω) decreases on binding ($12.94 \rightarrow 10.41$ eV), consistent with the decrease in μ magnitude and the small increase in hardness: the complex is predicted to be somewhat less electrophilic than the free ligand.

Taken together, these descriptors describe a chemically sensible outcome. Coordination to Cu(II) perturbs, but does not dramatically reorganize, the ligand’s frontier electronic structure: the ligand still retains its conjugation and the complex does not become substantially more reactive or unstable. The results accord with common observations in N,O-chelating systems where metal coordination raises ligand orbital energies and produces only modest changes in the HOMO–LUMO separation, particularly for first-row metal(II) complexes that do not introduce strongly delocalized metal-centered states near the ligand frontier orbitals.

4. CONCLUSION

The successful synthesis and comprehensive characterization of the copper(II) complex of 4-aminoantipyrine (4-AAP) have demonstrated that coordination with Cu(II) significantly enhances both the physicochemical and biological properties of the ligand. 4-AAP functions as a bidentate ligand, coordinating through both its amine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen atoms, according to spectroscopic investigations and DFT computations. The elevated melting point and a moderate HOMO–LUMO gap demonstrate the complex's enhanced thermal stability and significant electronic structural changes. The complex's superior antibacterial activity over the free ligand, especially against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, is noteworthy and highlights the possibility of using metal coordination as a tactic to increase the bioefficacy of well-known medicinal drugs. These results enhance our knowledge of 4-AAP metal complexes and lend credence to their further study as viable options for the creation of metal-based antibacterial drugs.

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